

A Data Science Support Team for ALVSCE at The University of Arizona

TABLE OF CONTENTS

JUSTIFICATION	1
PREVIOUS WORK AND PRESENT OUTLOOK	3
OBJECTIVES	6
PROCEDURE	6
PROBABLE DURATION	12
FINANCIAL SUPPORT	12
PERSONNEL	12
INSTITUTIONAL UNITS INVOLVED	12
COOPERATION	13
CRIS SEARCH	13
LITERATURE CITATIONS	13
SUGGESTED REVIEWERS	16

JUSTIFICATION:

Background:

Data science principles are an integral part of next-generation agriculture research (King 2017, Coble et al. 2018, Lew et al. 2020). Increasingly large and complex datasets are being collected and analyzed, such as via high-throughput plant phenotyping (Singh et al. 2016), spatial and temporal remote sensing probes (de Araujo Barbosa et al. 2015), and wearable sensors (Witt et al. 2019). According to PIs funded by NSF's BIO Directorate, the ability to manage, share, store, and publish data was identified as the most important needs (Barone et al. 2017).

Data-intensive science encompasses **custom pipelines and software tools** to produce efficient analyses, **effective data management** approaches, and **principles of open science** (Grahe 2018) and **reproducible research**. This shift is evidenced by journals and funding agencies that increasingly expect researchers to publish open code and data alongside their manuscripts and grant-supported research. New tools and methods make it easier than ever, and

the speed of science is accelerating as a result. Many modern **statistical and analytical tools** (e.g., Bayesian models, machine learning, automated pipelines, and interactive dashboards) are being published as open source software available as R and Python libraries. While data collection techniques, theory, and statistical methods vary across scientific research domains, a common theme is that cutting edge research benefits from data science best practices (Sandve et al. 2013, Wilson et al. 2014).

Data Science Needs at UA CALS:

The proposed project will support the Communications & Cyber Technologies Data Science Team (CCT Data Science) within the Division of Agriculture, Life & Veterinary Sciences, and Cooperative Extension (ALVSCE) at the University of Arizona. ALVSCE includes the College of Agriculture and Life Sciences, The Arizona Experiment Station, and Cooperative Extension, and is hereafter referred collectively to as CALS. CALS includes ten colleges, six agricultural research stations, and twenty three cooperative extension offices across Arizona. CALS represents diverse areas of research and extension, and supports the educational, agricultural, and economic needs of the citizens of Arizona.

CALS has prioritized developing data-intensive research and associated capacity at all career stages. This need has been a common theme across multiple internal reports that directly inform our group's priorities. One of the agricultural research stations is Communications & Cyber Technologies (CCT), co-located with CALS administration on the University of Arizona campus. This proposal will fund a data science focused team in CCT to serve CALS.

- The CALS Cyberinfrastructure Needs Report (McCarthy et al. 2018) prioritizes data science training for the next generation of plant/soil scientists, nutritionists, and resource economists. This report presents results of a faculty survey that identified needs including *training* in programming, data management, and data analytics and *technical support* for developing, deploying and maintaining databases. The report specifically requests a group of data scientists and systems administrators to assist with cyberinfrastructure and data management. *CCT Data Science was founded that year.*
- The CALS Data Science Ambassadors have conducted two surveys in the last two years. Rutherford (2020) surveyed graduate students and found that over two thirds of respondents identified a need for additional training in programming and statistics. In 2021, the data science ambassadors (unpublished) surveyed CALS graduate and undergraduate students and found that an overwhelming majority identified data science skills as important for their career.
- The CALS Career Competency Development Plan¹ identifies “Data-Informed Decision Making” as one of six career competencies and "Digital Literacy" as a top employment skill.

¹ career.cals.arizona.edu/resources/cals-competencies-plan

The CCT Data Science team² was founded in 2018 to meet these needs. CCT Data Science continuously interacts with and learns the needs of faculty and students across CALS; we have received further requests for training in foundational computing skills as well as project specific training and support for research computing.

While there are many resources available to learn data science skills and tools, there is a gap between learning and application. Resources are available within and outside of CALS, courses at the undergraduate and graduate level, and workshops provided by the Data Science Institute, the UA Libraries, UITS, CyVerse, and The Carpentries. While CCT Data Science works closely with these groups, it remains challenging for researchers to translate training into modern research practices related to data and computing. The CALS Cyberinfrastructure Needs Report (McCarthy et al. 2018) stated that some CALS unit leaders “were enthusiastic about applying these technologies to their work but unsure how to achieve this”.

CCT Data Science intends to be the go-to group for applying data science to research and accelerating knowledge transfer between researchers and stakeholders across CALS; we aim to enhance UA's leadership among the larger scientific community.

PREVIOUS WORK AND PRESENT OUTLOOK:

Within CALS, there is demand for domain-specific support to address different data computational needs. Our CCT Data Science team provides CALS researchers help with key mechanisms including development of **custom pipelines and software tools**, **effective data management**, **open and reproducible research**, and **statistical and analytical tools**.

CCT Data Science has created multiple means of engagement to deliver custom research support, training, and to build capacity across CALS. Briefly, we host weekly drop-in **office hours** as well as one-on-one consulting as needed. These sessions may solve a researchers' problem or serve as the initial conversation about more complex problems. For these targeted yet complex challenges, we offer extended research support through the **Data Science Incubator** program. The incubator was launched in summer 2021 to provide researchers with up to 80 hours of consultation and co-working with a CCT Data Science data scientist or software engineer. Our team is also available for **longer term collaborations**, such as writing external proposals or being hired part time as a data scientist or software engineer for particular projects. To upskill CALS researchers, we design and teach **workshops** that deliver practical data science content with direct research applications. Our monthly Workshop Wednesday covers a range of topics and our annual workshop series focuses on Reproducibility and Data Science; we also provide custom training for research groups by request. Finally, CCT Data Science actively **builds community** within and outside of UA by facilitating events, programs, and networking opportunities among aspiring and current data science practitioners.

² datascience.cals.arizona.edu

Below, we describe how each of our data science domains are delivered through one or more means of engagement.

Building pipelines and tools

Building infrastructure to support data science has been a cornerstone of our work and is based on deep understanding of our audience of research scientists. For example, we host a Drone Interest Group³ across UA's campus to understand the software needs of drone users. Our software contributions range in scale from developing the analysis pipeline for the world's largest agricultural robot at the Maricopa Agricultural Center (Burnette et al. 2018), a novel analysis framework for ecosystem modeling (Fer et al. 2020), automated daily ecological forecasting systems, and interactive visualizations that make high dimensional data accessible to scientists. The Drone Processing Pipeline (DPP), is an open source workflow developed by our group that focuses on simplifying the scaling of user contributed algorithms (Schnauffer et al. 2020). DPP has been integrated into scientific gateways including the CyVerse Discovery Environment and PlantIT, and has been applied to other geospatial analysis of plot and field level imagery. In another NSF-funded project, we collaborated with machine learning experts to deliver automated daily forecasts of plant phenology across 18 sites in the US, which are part of a forthcoming manuscript on comparing model efficacy (Raiho et al, *in prep*). For CALS incubator projects, we have built interactive dashboards for diverse data sources (e.g., soil moisture⁴, volatile organic compounds⁵) that allow our collaborators to visualize high-dimensional data interactively. Another incubator project with Laura Meredith (SNRE) produced an R package for calculating volatility of organic compounds automatically, replacing a manually-populated spreadsheet. By carefully considering and responding to the needs of researchers, CCT Data Science is able to make data science methods accessible.

Harmonizing and managing data

With increasing data volume and variety, the management and alignment of datasets for synthesis and reuse is a key challenge, but also an opportunity for synthetic research. CCT Data Science helps to develop and apply standards for agricultural and ecological data. We work with communities including ARDN⁶, BrAPI⁷, PEcAn⁸, EFI⁹, and TERRA-REF¹⁰ to develop and use standard formats and methods that enable sharing and reuse. CCT Data Science has contributed our expertise to community recommendations related to managing soil data (Todd-Brown et al.

³ drones.arizona.edu

⁴ viz.datascience.arizona.edu/rainman-soildata

⁵ viz.datascience.arizona.edu/VOC-timeseries

⁶ agmip.github.io/ARDN

⁷ brapi.org

⁸ pecanproject.org

⁹ ecoforecast.org

¹⁰ terraref.org

2021), leaf-level gas exchange data (Ely et al. 2021), data from breeding trials (Selby et al. 2019) and community infrastructure for crop and ecosystem modeling (Fer et al. 2020).

In CALS, we help in writing and implementing data management plans. For example, worked with the RainManSR rainfall manipulation experiment to develop protocols and training for data management (Data Makeover incubator). And we help publish data and code alongside manuscripts that we write, for example (LeBauer et al. 2020, 2021b, 2022, LeBauer and Guo 2021). We led construction of the computing pipeline for field scanner at the Maricopa Agricultural Station (Burnette et al. 2018), and produced the world's largest open dataset dedicated to agricultural research (LeBauer et al. 2020, 2021a).

Enhancing reproducibility and open science approaches

Open science principles to support reproducibility have been increasingly adopted by federal agencies and academic journals. However, researchers are often unsure of what tools and approaches they can use to meet the requirements of open science. We adopt and refine these practices in the projects we work on. CCT Data Science also offers training to the CALS research community. One successful effort is our Reproducibility and Data Science in R workshop series¹¹, which combines eight sessions of hands-on lessons with a student showcase of how they applied concepts to their research projects. Workshop participants demonstrated greatly improved skills with programming and developing reproducible, version-controlled workflows that make their research easier to conduct. We also supported the UA BRIDGES NSF Research Traineeship program in ecosystem genomics to provide a version of the workshop to their trainees, with a similar intent of giving the trainees the concepts and tools needed to proactively implement open science principles.

A final aim of our group is to connect researchers in CALS with wider campus initiatives including the Data Science Institute, CyVerse, and the UA Library. For example, we helped make RStudio Connect available to researchers on campus to easily deploy reports and interactive dashboards to facilitate discovery and collaboration. And, we have trained CALS researchers in the use of library resources including the Open Science Framework and the new ReDATA research repository to organize and share their research products.

Applying statistical and analytical tools

Statistical methods such as Bayesian modeling and machine learning can help domain researchers gain additional insight from their data. Here are some examples:

- 1) Riemer applied machine learning methods to annotate rangeland reports, which can now be searched by land managers through the Rangeland Docs portal¹².
- 2) With Elise Gornish (Extension), Guo developed a series of hierarchical Bayesian models

¹¹ datascience.cals.arizona.edu/spring-2022-workshop-series-reproducibility-and-data-science-skills

¹² docs.rangelandsgateway.org

to compare the effects of different management techniques on the prevalence of *Bromus tectorum*, an invasive grass (Gornish et al. in review, GitHub¹³).

- 3) Used models developed at the Maricopa Agricultural Center to predict future yield of *Agave americana* under different irrigation and mulching regimes (Davis et al. 2021, LeBauer et al. 2022).
- 4) With Isaac Mpanga (Extension), Guo and LeBauer utilized Bayesian techniques to estimate missing data and understand trends in organic agriculture production (LeBauer and Guo 2021, Mpanga et al. 2021).

We also teach statistical and analytical methods as part of the monthly Workshop Wednesday series, during office hours, at campus events and at national meetings. As in-house collaborators, CCT Data Science is able to contribute deep statistical knowledge and familiarity with a broad range of field, lab, and data driven research methods.

OBJECTIVES:

Our work advances the following strategic objectives.

- I. **Enabling research:** helping scientists overcome barriers to the use of data and computational methods, and facilitating collaboration among scientists, engineers, statisticians, and computer scientists.
- II. **Training:** training researchers individually and in small groups on tools, workflows, and approaches.
- III. **Community building and outreach:** facilitating communication, collaboration, and skills sharing among researchers interested in data science.

PROCEDURE:

Our approach is aimed at supporting our three core objectives: **Enabling research**, **Training**, and **Community building**. This is not a typical research proposal, but a proposal to support a program that enables and advances a diverse range of research and extension across CALS and beyond. As such, we are continually evolving to meet the challenges and opportunities that arise and support new people and projects. Our protocols are described in detail on our wiki¹⁴ and group website¹⁵.

I. Enabling Research and Extension

¹³ github.com/cct-datascience/rangeland-restore

¹⁴ osf.io/tzmhp

¹⁵ datascience.cals.arizona.edu/

CCT Data Science enables research and extension through a number of specific activities aimed at build data science capacity within CALS.

We hold open **office hours** weekly and by appointment. Office hours provide an easy and low pressure avenue for people to ask questions, solve problems, learn more about how we can help, and have open ended conversations. Such interactions sometimes turn into longer term relationships where we provide support and feedback. We also contact members of the CALS community to learn more about and identify ways we can support their data science needs.

For projects that warrant an extended scope of effort, we provide support through the **Data Science Incubator** program¹⁶. The Incubator program is one of our core offerings, and is based on similar short term support programs including the Incubator at the University of Washington eScience Institute¹⁷ and the XSEDE Extended Collaborative Support Program¹⁸. Project leads apply to work with us to define and propose a clear scope of work and clear outcomes. Outcomes typically include one or more of manuscripts, data, software, methods, protocols, proposals, and data dashboards. We work with project members not only to provide support, but also so that all involved can develop new skills. Previous incubator projects have resulted in scientific manuscripts, data publications, an R package, reproducible research compendia, interactive data visualizations, and a project-wide data management framework, protocols, and training. For Incubator projects, we budget up to four weeks FTE equivalent. This is split into approximately two weeks of direct engagement to complete the proposed work and up to two weeks of indirect 'behind the scenes' support. This 'behind the scenes' work happens at all stages, from pre-proposal community engagement and brainstorming, doing background research, project planning, writing and evaluating proposals. Post-project follow up includes finalizing publications and other scientific outputs, writing proposals to support further work, and longer term maintenance and check-ins.

In addition to training and research support, we help researchers at UA by providing support at the **proposal writing** stage. Our emphasis is on collaborative proposals led by UA PIs. Typically, this results in members of the CCT Data Science team as co-PIs or Senior Personnel. Our contributions primarily focus on data access and stewardship, novel analysis, and / or cyberinfrastructure. We occasionally lead proposals to support software, cyberinfrastructure, data harmonization, training, and outreach aligned with the ALVSCE mission. A few of these key projects have had lower success, and leading such proposals was de-emphasized starting last year. This has allowed us to prioritize playing a supporting role in proposals led by CALS faculty. The external funding we seek primarily provides salary support. But external funding does not support proposal writing, which is why proposal writing is included in the present scope of work.

¹⁶ datascience.cals.arizona.edu/incubator

¹⁷ escience.washington.edu/get-involved/incubator-programs

¹⁸ xsede.org/for-users/ecss

Target metrics:

- As a group, do weekly office hours and ad-hoc meetings, with at least 50 unique CALS researchers helped over the course of the year
- As a group, contribute to five proposals submitted per year as PIs or senior personnel
- Per 1.0 FTE equivalent salary support, complete six incubators per year

II. Training

Core training in data science and computing skills is aimed at bridging the gap between current skills and adoption of new methods and tools. Researcher productivity is often limited by bottlenecks in data management and analysis with software. Frequently, researchers are not aware of what modern computing methods exist, or how to choose and learn a new approach that may require short term investment and may (or may not) pay off. Furthermore, funding agencies, journals, and scientific communities are increasingly recognizing the value of open science approaches, including making computational research reproducible and easier to share.

Previous surveys have identified a rich ecosystem of courses and training opportunities on the UA campus and in the broader research community (McCarthy et al. 2018, Rutherford 2020). Our training aims to fill the gap between the more foundational instruction and the application of new techniques to research. This requires a good amount of foundational training, which we do in coordination with other groups on campus.

members of the current team (LeBauer, Guo, Riemer, and Scott) are certified Carpentries instructors and have PhDs in a CALS related scientific domain.

Our training includes both shorter targeted workshops and multi-part workshop series. For the former, we host monthly **Workshop Wednesdays**¹⁹, which are 1-2 hour workshops or demonstrations. The topics vary and are intermediate level, and are increasingly by request to target specific needs of researchers. During targeted workshops, we walk researchers through how to create useful tools or workflows, including reproducible reports, databases, and APIs, and give them the opportunity to implement these in their own research with our help.

We also developed a workshop series called **Reproducibility and Data Science Skills**²⁰ that is more intensive and provides a foundation of computational research skills and best practices in scientific computing. We meet with a group of researchers repeatedly over several months, teaching project management and documentation, intermediate programming, and version control. Key to how we teach is our philosophy of leaving no person behind and our practice of providing context for how to implement tools in practice. These foundational courses are useful for building capacity that gives all researchers the confidence and ability to practice appropriate modern computing. Furthermore, the workshop series provides skills required for our more

¹⁹ datascience.cals.arizona.edu/workshops

²⁰ datascience.cals.arizona.edu/spring-2022-workshop-series-reproducibility-and-data-science-skills

advanced workshops and incubator projects, and creates community across CALS departments, connecting otherwise siloed grad students and postdocs.

We will develop a formal **assessment system** to evaluate the success of our training, as well as to identify needs and challenges faced by CALS researchers. Evaluations allow us to determine if our training is meeting these needs. In the final session of the workshop series, we host a showcase for trainees to demonstrate how they have applied these new skills to their own research; this is a precursor for the Data Demo Day described in the following section.

We participate in existing **communities of practice** around data science skills training and create new communities both at UA and beyond. We model open and reproducible science by providing our curriculum and workshop recordings openly online. We will continue to coordinate our data science training with other groups and events on campus, such as the Data Science Institute, Research Bazaar Tucson²¹, Data and Software Carpentries, and formal coursework. Workshop participants are encouraged to work together, and provided avenues of communication such as Slack channels to do so, to troubleshoot and further their skills. We recruit advanced and enthusiastic workshop participants and community members to reinforce their new skills by teaching them, offering opportunities to be helpers at our workshops or teach their own. We also engage with external communities of data science research, software, and education, including R4DS, The Carpentries, Earth System Information Partners, Ecological Forecasting Initiative, the PEcAn Project, the Agricultural Research Data Network, Drones2Phenomes, the North American Plant Phenotyping Network, and the CGIAR Big Data Platform in Agriculture.

Members of our group will continue to grow our own skill sets through **professional development** opportunities to continue to stay on the cutting edge of computational tools and data science approaches as applied to research. We will participate in pedagogical training to further improve our teaching and assessment skills. Additionally, we attend conferences and workshops to learn new research software development and data science skills, in order to be best suited to train and collaborate with researchers.

Target metrics:

- As a group, teach eight two hour targeted workshops per year (last Wednesday of the month)
- As a group, teach one foundational workshop series per year (fall semester)
- Publish training materials (typically on GitHub²² and YouTube²³)
- Each member does at least one professional development activity each year
- Each member learns and applies a minimum of one new skill and one new research area each year.

²¹ researchbazaar.arizona.edu

²² github.com/cct-datascience/CALS-workshops

²³ youtube.com/channel/UCiBfho07gp4LMbWY3_EG8Iw/videos

III. Community Building and Outreach

Given the large size and important mission of CALS, CCT Data Science can not support every research project. Rather than directly engaging with each research project in a hub and spoke model, we build data science capacity and confidence following a **cascade model**. In our cascade model, CCT Data Science cultivates individual expertise and facilitates cross-fertilization across research domains. Common themes of **custom pipelines and software tools, data management, open and reproducible research, and statistical and analytical tools** emerge. This section describes our procedure for amplifying the reach of CCT Data Science across the CALS community and beyond.

Leveraging UA people, events, and institutions

CCT Data Science takes active leadership roles among the data science community at The University of Arizona. For example, Riemer, Guo, and LeBauer have served on the organizing committee of Women in Data Science (WiDS Tucson²⁴). WiDS Tucson is a community-organized event that communicates the scholarship and achievements of women/non-binary data scientists, broadly defined. Guo organized the Research Bazaar Arizona annual conference in 2022, where Riemer and LeBauer have taught workshops and participated in career panels. We also regularly participate in Research Bazaar meetups, and co-locate our office hours with Coffee and Code each Tuesday.

While CCT Data Science primarily serves the needs of CALS researchers, we also recognize the value of leveraging the research and training capacity across UA institutions. Thus, we coordinate with other data science and research computation entities on campus. For projects or questions we do not have capacity or are less suited to support, we direct researchers to other campus resources. We also **foster collaborations** with other UA data science groups, including mentoring the Data Science Institute data science ambassador(s) for CALS, co-teaching workshops with Data Science Institute trainers, and working with the CyVerse science and education teams.

As our audience of research trainees (graduate students and post-doctoral researchers) turn over regularly, one problem lies in cultivating new practitioners of data science to the point where they can nimbly interact with CCT Data Science. The Carpentries offers a well-vetted introductory curriculum for computational skills, but can lack organizers to facilitate regular sessions for students. We will team up with Katy Prudic and Ellen Bledsoe (SNRE) to organize a two-day Carpentries workshop annually. Rather than always teach ourselves, we will identify promising and enthusiastic practitioners from our intermediate workshops or collaborations to become certified Carpentries instructors.

Finally, as the CALS Data Science needs survey revealed, graduate students strongly desire more formal coursework with data science components, which can be mismatched with the

²⁴ widstucson.org

current statistical methods classes that most CALS departments offer. We will collaborate with the Data Science Institute to offer course redesign support for faculty wishing to add data science components to their courses. For example, Emily Butler (FSHD) is interested in working with CCT Data Science to broaden the reach of her Bayesian regression course.

Growing the community

CCT Data Science embraces a broad and inclusive definition of a data scientist. Even so, early career CALS researchers may be reluctant to claim the mantle. We are developing two programs to encourage the CALS community to **engage with data science solutions** to their research problems. We will annually hold CALS Data Demo Day that includes lightning research presentations and demonstrations. Rather than presenting their research, participants will enumerate a specific problem and showcase a data science solution. A ‘poster session’ with large monitors will be set up afterward for attendees to view the problem and solution in action, and a guest panel of judges will offer written feedback. Second, we will offer a summer data management fellowship, modeled after the one offered by the Environmental Data Initiative. CALS mentors seeking to reorganize their lab or project will be paired with a trainee, who has undergone training from the CCT Data Science team in reproducibility and best practices. In this way we can enhance the reach of individual Data Makeover incubator projects and help researchers implement data management practices to meet funding agency requirements. We will develop, and run additional events that promote data science in CALS as new opportunities arise.

Bridging domain boundaries

Academic research often takes place in silos, and data science approaches are one effective way of **bridging the gaps** that effectively isolate different research domains. For example, the Drone Interest Group led by Schnauffer and LeBauer gathers drone enthusiasts across domains including agriculture, journalism, and optical engineering to share approaches and troubleshoot problems during monthly meetings. The first Drone Demo Day²⁵ (March 23, 2022) was a successful in-person meeting that combined research talks with field testing of drone equipment. We foresee additional interest groups, such as ‘multivariate modeling’ and ‘machine learning’, that can similarly unite practitioners of analytical tools.

Target metrics:

- As a group, organize two community building events per year (e.g., Drone Day and Data Demo Day)
- Each member will be the designated liaison for a larger initiative (e.g., WiDS, Research Bazaar, DSRT)

²⁵ <https://drones.arizona.edu/ua-drone-day-2022>

PROBABLE DURATION:

October 1, 2022 - September 30, 2027

FINANCIAL SUPPORT:

Beyond the scope of work proposed here, our team will continue to be funded by other sources. Since its founding in 2018, our program has been supported by a combination of startup and federal grants, primarily to PI LeBauer. We have brought in more than \$2 million in funding, primarily as salary support, from agencies including NSF, USDA, DOE, ARPA-E, and DARPA. We have also been funded at much smaller amounts on the order of \$5-50k by existing projects. Startup funds were provided by CALS Associate Dean of Research Parker Antin. The group has helped write well over a dozen proposals. We will continue to apply for funding from these and other agencies, and also to provide part time support for other programs that have a need for our skills, where hiring a software engineer or data science is impractical. Starting in June 2022, the Data Science Institute provides partial salary support (approximately 0.5 FTE) to extend our group's education and outreach activities across campus.

We expect to continue to obtain additional funding by participating from the proposal stage as well as by supporting funded projects that need less than full time support. This will include projects that grow beyond the support provided through for Incubator projects, and by providing short-term support for funded projects. This projects' core Hatch funding enables the stability and flexibility to meet diverse needs, and to support programs and projects that do not have the resources to hire and manage a full time data scientist or software engineer.

PERSONNEL:

Leaders:

David LeBauer, PhD, Director of Data Science (PI)

Kristina Riemer, PhD, Scientific Programmer (co-PI)

Jessica Guo, PhD, Data Scientist (co-PI)

Other project personnel:

Matt Rahr, Director, Cyber & Information Technologies

Chris Schnauffer, Research Software Engineer

Eric Scott, PhD, Research Programmer and Educator

INSTITUTIONAL UNITS INVOLVED:

Communications and Cyber Technologies Data Science Team (CCT-DS)

COOPERATION:

We work w/ multiple USDA researchers and units affiliated with UA. We also collaborate with the National Agriculture Library and USDA funded projects including ARDN and AG2PI.

CRIS SEARCH:

We searched the CRIS database (cris.nifa.usda.gov/search.html) for Hatch projects once with the term 'data science' and found seven results, all of which focus on narrowly scoped research projects. We then repeated the search with the term 'statistics' and found sixty four Hatch projects. Some of these projects were less narrowly focused, but none were of a similarly broad scope, as the proposed project. The closest project in scope was project number NYC-151403, "Statistical consulting for the statutory colleges at Cornell." which ran from 1998-2004 and ARZT-1360030-H22-137 "Statistics consulting laboratory" which ran from 2012-2016. Both of these projects have been terminated, and were more restricted in the range of activities supported.

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